

Modern-day Leadership

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Abstract:

Leadership is a challenging thing and in the present scenario it has a completely different perspective, as a head you are equally responsible for the others deeds. In the present scenario it's not only about the high intelligence part it's also the amount of emotional stability. In this article we have discussed the important traits required for the effective leadership and its do's and don'ts while dealing with all sorts of employees, especially the amount of delegation required and the accountability on the individual part.

Keywords:

Characteristics required, Empathy towards all, Delegation of work, avoiding micromanagement, Result oriented

Introduction:

Leadership is the most crucial aspect of any organization. In the earlier time it was comparatively much easier to hold the position of leader, this we can say because in the past period of 30-35 years ago, it was much easier because of less opportunities, less awareness among the masses and also less technical awareness, because of these aspects people were less complicated mainly because of lack of awareness, most of the employees were more obedient and sincere, for them their command (Immediate boss/leader) is my wish. In the present day things are not like that because now in one organization, leadership is delegated into various parts, like for example several reporting system. Most of the things and protocols are not even clear to those who are working in the same organization.

In this article, I am trying to introduce the concept of modern day leadership, as we all know leader is the most important pillar of any organization and in the present day the concept of leader has changed because of many reasons like advancement and more awareness, earlier like in all the sectors, more advancement and more awareness has come to the role of the leadership. Nowadays the role of a leader is more demanding and having more expectation management factor on the concerned person and there is always the pressure to prove the expectation or in simple terms to prove their worth to all. The role of a leader depends on the success and achievement of the organization. In the current arena the leadership is divided into several pieces, in the present time even the immediate boss also considers them as a leader and technically they are not wrong in describing them, because they are the leader of their group/department/sector and most of the time considered to be accountable for them.

Characteristics required: -

Most of the characteristics like great visionary, emotionally strong, self-discipline, hardworking and dedicated were earlier also. These characteristics are coming from the ages (mainly past years) and to some extent it is going in a very similar track like controlling the situation, as it is expected from the leader to take control of the situation completely under their hand. In the present time and with the present generation it is not sufficient and so easy to

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control the complete situation under their hand especially at the arrival of Zen-G generation in the work force, the work culture has affected because this generation has a different mindset and follow different approach in dealing individuals. There is no denying that every individual is different in everything, different approach also different way of dealing and taking things on personal level. The characteristics cannot be prominent on anyone, but certainly few attributes of leadership like effective speaker, managing various individual well and most important should not be biased towards anyone. Hence following characteristics are required

- (1) Empathy towards all** – In the organization there are people of all age group and all of them cannot be treated in the same manner, some are older and some are slight younger. Firstly, as a leader all you need to make sure that all should be treated as per their designation and experience, age cannot be the parameter of their privileged, like the one who is younger is pampered like a child or the baby of the family and because of this they are careless of the assigned task or task given without any accountability. Similarly, the one who is senior in age is treated like a post - retired person, given attention and preference but it should not be over, there should be a balance between senior and junior work –force, also both of them should be respected accordingly and the one who is senior is expected to be respected but at the same time the younger employee should be treated respectfully.
- (2) Playing favoritism** –In every organization each leader has its favorite people and it is nothing wrong if we think this on the leader’s perspective but it becomes awkward situation when others also know this and in maximum cases it is visible to others also, because other employees also want to flaunt that we are so important members of the organization and most important we are the big boss favorite people. Frankly speaking this situation never helps any individual and the organization for the long run because everything is open to all that who is the favorite one and those who are favorite they try to sustain their position and while sustaining the position of the favorite person of the team, they actually harm the organization and in a way their immediate boss also. Like while sustaining their position they bring lot of non-relevant things on the front table like gossip and bitching becomes the most important aspect of hiring and firing someone. Second harm comes in an indirect way when such people (favorite one) gets special treatment by the senior members of the team also getting privileged and special treatment on all the occasions.
- (3) Become a mystery:-** Every individual has its own way of dealing things, but when you are holding important position, you cannot afford to be obvious all the time with your way of handling things, like similar way of reacting in a typical situation. The situation becomes more worst when people even understand and calculate your mood swings. The best way to deal is to show minimum emotions and react less with every individual and situations, although it becomes very difficult to react less, sometimes the situation proves other way but the head of the organization need to maintain the calm and show less emotions.
- (4) Result oriented strategy:-** The strategies which are planned has to be result oriented, if the strategies are not focused or showing some outcome, then there is no use of implementing those planning, also one need to remember that all new ideas are not always fruitful and the old one are not always wastage. At the very initial level the planning and the strategies which the leader implements are very crucial for any organization. So, when it is not giving any result that would be a considered as complete fiasco for the team and especially for the individual as a whole.

In many corporate houses and also in the academics most of the time is being wasted in the unnecessary meetings and protocols which is actually is the wastage of time, most of the meetings have fixed strategies, secondly in such meeting maximum people avoid speaking on the true concern, in fact most of the time is on the blame game theory or targeting any particular individual.

- (5) **Delegation of work:** - Some of the work which can be easily done others, should be allotted to them only, because you cannot be omnipresent everywhere secondly it would be better for the head person's smooth functioning of work. Although some the person's might not agree with this because they feel that the whole authority should be centralized and to them only, that is only effective for the smaller organizations but for larger organizations it only shows the insecurity of the concerned person and also not very effective for the longer run for the organization. Secondly most important thing is that when some person is given onus to perform the work, they will surely give their best to perform that task, it is the maximum tendency to perform better when given some responsibility because responsibility automatically brings accountability. Hence the task should be allotted to the concerned persons as per their caliber to perform that task.
- (6) **Avoiding micromanagement:** - There should be proper space should be given to the person, over monitoring or targeting some person cannot make that person to perform better although it has become a trend in many organizations for the excessive monitoring of the employees which only reduces the work efficiency of the employees. Most of the employers feel that creating insecurity atmosphere will improve the efficiency of the work force, which is completely wrong, because unnecessary stress and anxiety will only give harm to the organization.
- (7) **Hard work should be appreciated:** -In most of the organization there are people who show that they are working because they are mostly on the front line, but there is a category which actually works but never comes into picture, as a head it is the responsibility to see that who is actually working and who is not. The problems start when the immediate boss/head is started getting insecure with the people who are working under him, it only happens when the leadership is imposed on the non-deserving employees, when the leadership is strong, such problem never arises. It is the responsibility of the higher authority that the persons who are leading should be efficient enough to lead the team from the front, because when the non-deserving person is on the top they try to find the scape goat within the team, so that they are protected and they can put the blame on the other person.
- (8) **Positive Body language:** - The body language needs to be confident and appealing, the leadership should not be imposing on you neither it should be very dominating or controlling. The positive gestures mean the moment a person looks at others positivity comes instantly. For example, confident handshake, looking at all when addressing in the meeting (proper eye contact), showing warm and accepting body language.
- (9) **Orator:-** It is one of the crucial characteristics of the effective leadership, a good leader is supposed to be good with the words and most important needs to possess effective communication, or in more simple words, he is clearly understood by the others. It is a human tendency that people listen to the good speakers, they automatically get connected to them while listening. It is certainly considered one of the best quality of the good leadership, many famous leaders in the past were gifted of this quality also in the present time in our nation as well as in the international arena, We find good examples of effective speakers.

(10) Humanitarian aspect: - The humanitarian aspect should always be on the top priority, a good leader always makes things better for others, the saddest and dictatorship cannot sustain on the longer period. People notice even small things when they are judging the leaders their way of treating other staff, how many times they are smiling, acknowledging their staff presence or not. In the present scenario maximum people are practical in their approach and sometimes being extra practical actually reduces the humanitarian aspect. Secondly the decisions should never be taken rashly the other party should always get a chance to prove its worth. Like for example if the head of the family has a strong dislike for some individual and he even stop acknowledging the wishes and at the other end they are being extra generous and polite for some other staff member.

Drawbacks of effective leadership: -When you are at the top position, it is not easy to manage people easily, most of the people in your department either like you or they don't like you. Things don't get easy for the leader's or the one who is holding the top position, there are certain loop holes which need to be addressed like

A. Choose wisely your people: -First and the most important thing is to choose your people wisely, every important person has a habit of choosing and later on trusting their own people in the team, when the trust becomes it becomes trouble for others and later on for them also. In the team they are treated as the boss favorite person, which later on is visible and known to the whole team. Sometimes the favorite person brings his or her own grudges on the table which certainly satisfy their ego, but it is not good for the long run for the organization and certainly for the leader's perspective

When the leader start choosing shallow people and later on trusting them blindly it is not considered to be a good thing overall. While choosing the best person, the person holding the top position need to understand that their favorite person at least has some skill, knowledge and potential. Hence the decision should be completely based on the practical things rather than on the emotional aspect while choosing your people within the team.

B. Easily available: - When the leader is very much easily available for everybody, it has good factors and negative also like for example when the person is easily available it gives the picture that the person is so much available because of less of occupancy and when you are selective with your meeting, you have an image that may be because of occupancy they are not able to meet.

Secondly as a leader you should not entertain all the gossip which is coming to your table, because when you do that it only shows your shallowness and also negative approach.

C. Loosing empathy factor: -As a leader you always need to follow the humanitarian aspect and empathy towards others, it becomes slight difficult when you don't personally like the person and the hatred should not be visible on your face, not listening to them although you have a different approach towards people other people.

In many sectors it is seen that the head doesn't acknowledge to your wishes, whereas they acknowledge other person very nicely in front of others, they also sometimes dismiss your leaves, whereas very kind towards their favorite people. this kind of approach only brings toxicity in the atmosphere.

D. Avoiding major details: -As a leader complete work cannot be delegated to others the final say should be in your hand for every single thing happening in the organization and for that every small and minute details needs to be thoroughly checked before approving or implementing things in the organization.

E. Playing divide and rule policy: -The policy of divide and rule is a very old policy and most of the times it is successful, but now we have Zen-G Employees also in the organization and people from different mindset and approach and unfortunately this policy is now very old and in most of the places it is easily caught by the employees who are in the organization for more than 4-5 years. The older employees know your way of reacting, your approach. Hence this one in perspective of the present time is not always correct.

All the above mentioned things are important for any person who is holding the top position needs to be applied for the successful leadership.

Major areas to work on:-

- (1) **Delegation of task:-** The delegation task, should be done to others because it's a human tendency that a person when given importance does work more efficiently also makes others also do the same, apart from this also when a person is given importance his/her true personality is visible to others. Hence whenever the delegation task is given to the person, that has to be properly monitored and most important only deserving person should be assigned the task, because the whenever the non-deserving candidates is unnecessary promoted, they make others life hell.
- (2) **Final decision:** - As a leader even when the task has been assigned to others, still the final say should be in your hand and before making the final decision all the aspects should be considered properly before making the final say. Even if the head cannot afford to be physically present, but they need to have complete focus on the things which are surrounding by them, they should be aware of all the happenings around them.

Conclusion: - leadership is a very important thing for any person also it is very crucial for the whole organization, because the person holding the top position is also considered to be a trend setter for the whole organization. In the present time some people consider this as a burden, whereas on few individual its imposed on them. The ideal leader is the one who takes all the challenges in an effective manner, without getting emotional on any occasion. Most of the inexperienced people consider leadership as a dictatorship and for them it only means imposing things on others, whereas they forget that that the leaders job is to nurture others, the most deserving person should hold the top position, also people with high emotional stability should be promoted for the top place. The bitterness and toxic atmosphere should not be promoted and the most important thing is solutions should be promoted rather than cribbing and creating trouble for others, because as already said the leader is like a nurturing parent and people with such tendency only should be promoted at the top. It's a very old saying that when a deserving person is on the top nobody complains the problem occurs only when the non-deserving person is leading on the top, because such people only downgrade others to show their existence and the worst thing is that their survival only happens because of this trend.

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- *Editor's Note:* See article '[Global Leadership for Global Mission](https://lausanne.org/global-analysis/global-leadership-for-global-mission)' by Mary Ho in *Lausanne Global Analysis*, November 2016, <https://lausanne.org/global-analysis/global-leadership-for-global-mission>

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